

A simple, rapid and cost-effective method to isolate the huge quantity of human mononuclear cells from minute quantities of blood as well as buffy coat for different immunological and magnetic beads applications

Authors: Sudhir Bhatia and Gudrun Baersch, Genekam Biotechnology AG, Duissernstr. 65a, 47058 Duisburg, Germany Email: anfrage@genekam.de

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9881-7101>

Abstract:

Aim: Today the isolation of mononuclear cells (MNC) is being done with density gradient methods, which are cumbersome and time consuming, but need minimum 10 ml of buffy coat or blood to be performed, as this method is unable to isolate the MNC from minute volume like 100 μ l. Therefore, we decided to develop a simple, rapid and cost-effective method to isolate the MNC from minute volume of blood and buffy coat.

Methods. MNC isolator was used to isolate the MNC from 100 as well as 500 μ l of blood as well as buffy coat just mixing and centrifugation. Isolated cells were cultured and magnetic beads were used to isolate the CD4 and CD45 specific cells.

Results: In 15 experiments, MNC isolator were used successful to isolate MNC from minute volumes of blood and buffy coat. The cell cultured were generated and they were maintained up to 3 years without any contamination and the cells remain healthy. Successful isolation of CD4 and CD45 cells with magnetic beads war carried. The cells were frozen and thawed.

Conclusions: In this work, we developed first time a simple, cost effective and robust method to isolate MNC from minute volume of buffy coat and blood for immunological applications and magnetic beads cell isolation. The method is so simple that it can be used in any cell culture laboratory in the world. This method should open new opportunities to develop new kinds of antibodies, to isolate the different cell populations with magnetic beads as well as to get large number of T-cells for development of immunotherapies like CAR T-cell therapies.

Keywords: Mononuclear cell isolation, buffy coat, blood, CD4 positive cells, magnetic beads

Introduction: For many years, the applications using human mononuclear cells are on rise as these cells can be used to develop immunotherapies and production of human antibodies. (1,2,3,4) T-cells immunotherapies are increasing rapidly. Similarly, there is an increase in number of therapeutic antibodies to treat the cancer as well as viral diseases, which are being approved during the recent time for clinical use. To develop these all, one needs human mononuclear cells, where the specific cells e.g., CD8 T-cells are needed, therefore the isolation or sorting of such cells is an essential step. The fastest way to sort these cells is magnetic beads, where the negative as well as positive selection methods can be used along the sorting with flow cytometry. (5,6,7,8)

Till today, there is use of density gradient methods to isolate the MNC, where the user puts the buffy coat or blood diluted with PBS on the density gradient fluid very carefully so both should not mix,

otherwise the isolation of MNC is not possible. For use of the density gradient method, one needs minimum 10 ml of buffy coat or blood, the white layer is produced, from where user isolates the cells. There is a huge loss of cells during this process. To create T-cell therapies, there is a need of huge number of MNC. Density gradient method becomes here very expensive, cumbersome and time consuming for the development of these therapies. Along with the development of therapies, such MNC are being used for development and performance of a number of immunological assays like flow cytometry, ELISA etc. (9,10,11,12,13)

There are some publications claiming that they have isolated MNC from small volumes of blood, but they have used 5 and 10 ml of blood, there is no report how to isolate the MNC from minute volume like 100 μ l or more. (14,15) There are developments of automatic complex robotic systems for isolation of MNC, where the costs will be many thousands of dollars. (16, 17)

To produce the human antibodies, sometime user has very small quantity of blood or buffy coat available. Now the question arises how to isolate MSC from such a small quantity e.g., 100 or 500 μ l. Such small quantities cannot be used with density gradient method.

Therefore, our aim of the research work was to create a method, which can be used with minute volume of blood or buffy coat e.g., 100 μ l or more to generate MSC, to use them to create cell cultures and to use these MSC to isolate different lymphocytes expressing the following biomarkers like CD45, CD4, CD19 cells as examples.

Method: Total number of experiments shown in the work are 15. There are two different sources (buffy coats and blood) used during the experiments.

The buffy coats were obtained from Red Cross blood donation center, Germany and these were numbered that the donor cannot be identified, hence there is no need of any research ethic committee approval. The blood was donated through one of author of this publication to conduct the studies, there is an approval of research ethnic committee report of Genekam Biotechnology AG. (Number: 5.17)

100 μ l of buffy coat was mixed with 900 μ l of Genekam MNC isolator (1:5 ratio; prewarmed at 37 $^{\circ}$ C). It was kept at room temperature after gently vortexing and centrifuged at 1700 RMP for 5 minutes. The supernatant was discarded. The cells were washed twice with PBS (Biochrome, Germany) while centrifuging at 1700 RMP for 5 minutes. Sometime, there were some erythrocytes in the pellet, pellet was treated again with MNC isolation to remove them and washed once.

Counting the number of mononuclear cells was done with trypan blue staining in Neubauer Chamber under the microscope.

Similarly, 500 μ l of buffy coat was mixed with 4500 μ l Genekam MNC isolator and rest procedure was repeated as mentioned above. The blood samples were processed similarly as the steps done with blood.

To compare the results, the density gradient method was used with large volume of buffy coat. 10 ml of buffy coat was mixed with equal volume of PBS and it was layered on the density gradient solution (Biochrome) in such way that buffy coat and density gradient method do not mix with each. It was centrifuged and the upper layer was removed in order to collect the middle white ring. The cells were

washed with PBS twice while centrifuging at 1700 RMP and they were counted under microscope with trypan blue staining as mentioned somewhere.

Isolated MNC cells were cultured in DMEM / RPMI (Biochrome, Germany / Lonza, USA) with 1% Glutamine and 1% Streptopenicillin (Biochrome, Germany) in 2-3% fetal calf serum. (18) They were fed regularly and were processed for different experiments e.g., development of antibodies, conducting flow cytometry experiments as well as isolation of different fractions of lymphocytes. (Publications under development). The media was collected for conducting other experiments e.g., ELISA as well as presence of other molecules. (The procedure and data are not shown here as they are part of future publication) A part of cells was frozen for future use in DMSO freezing solution (Genekam). A large number of cells from cell cultures were frozen successfully and thawed for further use.

Magnetic beads isolation of CD4 and CD45 cells was done with the use of CD4 and CD45 magnetic beads (MICROBOSS Nanomedicine GmbH). A pellet was generated from isolated MNC or 3-5 ml of cultured MNC and to this 2 μ l or 5 μ l of magnetic beads were added. These microtubes were put in magnetic rack (Genekam, Germany). The magnetic beads were bound to CD4 or CD45 cells. They were washed with PBS twice. At the end, these cells were observed under microscope. They were used in other experiments. Similarly, CD19 magnetic beads were used to isolate the B-cells for further use.

Results: We are working with this method since 2013. We conducted more than 100 experiments, but in this publication, we are presenting only the results of 15 experiments as examples. (Table 1)

The results shown in Table 1 indicate that there was successful MSC isolation of all experiments using blood as well as buffy coat. The isolated MNC were successfully used to generate the cell cultures. At the beginning we isolated MNC from bigger volume buffy coats with density gradient method, as the number of isolated cells were very low against the number of isolated cells from 500 μ l of buffy coat, therefore we used only MNC isolator to generate MNC for our different experiments. (Picture 1) The number of isolated cells were so high that one has to dilute the pellet many folds to count the total number of isolated cells as one can see in the picture. The number of counted cells were around 900 million per ml of blood in one experiment and other experiment, it was around 400 million per ml against the density gradient method, where the number of isolated MNC varies between 0.7 million to 3 million in total. Sometimes, there were cell clumps in the cell cultures like collagenase in two experiments, but they did not have negative impact on the experiments, therefore no chemicals were used, moreover the clumps disappear in the cell culture after a few days. Isolated procedure was very simple than that of density gradient, where one must be very careful while adding the diluted buffy coat on density gradient media. Both should not mix, otherwise MNC cannot isolated. The procedure with MNC isolator was completed with in 30 minutes against the 50 minutes needed with density gradient solution.

There were successful isolations of MNC from 100 μ l (7 times) as well as 500 μ l (7 times) in all 15 experiments. Even there was successful isolation from volume less than 50 μ l. (Data not shown)

The cell cultures were created from isolated MNC successfully, where they were grown successfully in 2-3% FCS. From these cell cultures, CD45 specific and CD4 specific magnetic beads were used to isolate the specific cell populations. (Picture 2) The magnetic beads were attached on the surface of cells. CD5 specific beads attached to large of surface area of a cell. Similarly CD19 magnetic beads were used to isolate the CD19 B cells for experiments. (The publication in development)

Some of cell culture generated were run up to 3 years to conduct various experiments. Keeping such long period, the cell culture without any contamination indicate that this method can generate robust cell cultures for long term use.

The cell cultures were frozen successfully in DMSO based freezing media and they were thawed successfully to be used as cell cultures.

Discussion: In this work, we presented a reliable, cost effective and robust method to isolate the MNC cells from the small quantity of blood and buffy coat. The method is so simple that this can be used in any laboratory in the world. This method opens the opportunities to conduct the studies from small quantity of the buffy coat and blood. In many cases, there may be limited supply of these both e.g., chronic ill patients, which can serve the source of B-lymphocytes to generate the potential therapeutic antibodies as well as to conduct the studies on T-cells, this method provides huge number of lymphocytes, which may be very interesting for development of T-cell immunotherapies along with conducting other studies on them. Not only this, in our previous publication, we have shown that 2-3% FCS is sufficient to develop and maintain the MNC cultures and in these studies, we are providing further proof that smaller quantity of FCS can be used and user can save the money leading to reduction in the cost of development of applications MNC as 10% FCS is being used in most of the laboratories worldwide today. (18) The method developed in this work may offer a basis for development of new kind of automatic robotic machines with artificial intelligence, which may be likely to economical in development and production along with to generate the MNC in larger volume to serve the need of rising demand of immunotherapies against the costs and performance of robotic machines being used today. (17)

There was sometime very small contamination of erythrocytes in some experiments, but these have no negative on any of our experiments conducted, but we are working on a method to remove them completely.

In our laboratory, we are using this method regularly and generated number of interesting results and molecules, about which we are going to publish our work in the future.

Magnetic beads were used successfully to isolate the CD4 and CD45 T-cells, which were used in various applications, about these, there will be future publications. The cells were frozen and cultured successfully for future use. Such freezing and thawing open also further chances to conduct the new studies as well as ship the cells to other destinations.

Some cell cultures were used for 3 years for conducting experiments without contamination. It shows another advantage of this method.

Conclusion: In this work, we developed first time a simple, cost effective and robust method to isolate MNC from minute volume of buffy coat and blood. The method is so simple that it can be used in any cell culture laboratory in the world. This method should open new opportunities to develop new kinds of antibodies, to isolate the different cell populations with magnetic beads as well as to get large number of T-cells for development of immunotherapies like CAR T-cell therapies. It may act the basis of development of new robotic machines to meet the growing demand of MNC for various immunotherapies development and manufacturing.

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Table 1 shows MNC isolations with density gradient methods and MNC isolator and their different parameters.

Experiment	Density gradient method (volume)	MNC isolation (volume)	MNC isolation	Cell culture	Magnetic beads isolation (CD4 / CD8 / CD19)	Freezing and Thawing
1	+ (10 ml)		+	+		
2	+ (10 ml)	+ (500 µl)	+(++)	+		
3	+ (10 ml)	+ (500 µl)	+(++)	+	+	successful
4		+ (100 µl)	++	+		successful
5		+ (100 µl)	++	+	+	successful
6		+ (100 µl)	++	+	+	successful
7		+ (500 µl)	++	+	+	successful
8		+ (500 µl)	++	+	+	successful
9		+ (500 µl)	++	+	+	successful
10		+ (100 µl)	++	+	+	successful
11		+ (100 µl)	++	+	+	successful
12		+ (100 µl)	++	+	+	successful
13		+ (500 µl)	++	+	+	successful
14		+ (500 µl)	++	+	+	successful
15		+ (100 µl)	++	+	+	successful

Picture 1 shows isolated human MNC with MNC isolator from buffy coat under the microscope. (100X)

Picture 2 is showing the isolated CD45 positive cells from MNC under microscope. (100 X)